

Formation constants of some ternary lanthanide(III) chelates with vitamin U and oxine

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Abstract : Formation of 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complex species (MAL) has been inferred and the relevant equilibrium has been established from pH measurements on the interaction of M³⁺ ions [M = La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Sm^{III} and Gd^{III}] with ligand A [HA = oxine] in the presence of the ligand L [HL = vitamin U] in aqueous medium at ionic strength of 0.2 and at varying temperatures, 25 °C and 35 °C.

Keywords : Ternary lanthanoid(III) complexes, oxino, vitamin U.

The modified form of Irving-Rossotti¹ titration method is used to evaluate the ternary metal ligand stability constants at two different temperatures.

Results and discussion

The present communication describes the results of an equilibrium study on the mixed ligand complex formation of lanthanide(III) ions (M = La, Pr, Sm, Gd) with vitamin U (HL) (1) and oxine (HA) at 25 °C and 35 °C in aqueous solution at a fixed ionic strength 0.2 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄ solution.

(1) (HL)

The mixed ligand formation of 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes of M(III) were calculated by considering that 1 : 1 [M(III)A]²⁺ complex is completely formed and then after the coordination of the secondary ligand L takes place.

In the presence of secondary ligand, hydrolysis of [MA]²⁺ is suppressed therefore, there is formation of mixed ligand complex, [MAL]⁺ at higher pH. The degree of hydration of lanthanide ions [M(H₂O)₉]³⁺ is a subject of long debate. The ionic size and partial molal volume decrease from La³⁺ to Sm³⁺ until crowding of ligands becomes intense. The decrease in size, affects the coordination number of the metal ion, and as a result there is a decrease in coordination number. Other factors remaining same, the increase in acidity due to decrease in size facilitates better coordination. The log K_{MAL}^{MA} values are lower than that of the log K_{ML}^M values which are in the order of La-oxine-vitamin U < Pr-oxine-vitamin U < Sm-oxine-vitamin U < Gd-oxine-vitamin U as expected with respect to electronic configuration, size, Paulings electronegativity, ionic potential of trivalent metal ions, nature of the concerned ligands and stereochemistry of the complex.

Experimental

Oxine and vitamin U (Fluka), sodium perchlorate (Fluka), perchloric acid (B.D.H.) were used. Stock solutions of La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Sm^{III} and Gd^{III} perchlorate solutions were standardized by complexometric EDTA titrations². Carbonate-free NaOH solution was standardized by reported method³.

Note

Table 1. Proton ligand and metal ligand stability constants of lanthanide metal complexes of oxine (HA) and vitamin U (HL) at different temperatures ($\mu = 0.2 M NaClO_4$)

Temp	HL	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$			
		La^{III}	Pr^{III}	Sm^{III}	Gd^{III}
25 °C	$pK_1^H = 8.25$	5.62	5.67	5.72	5.78
	$pK_2^H = 2.17$				
35 °C	$pK_1^H = 8.15$	5.77	5.80	5.82	5.87
	$pK_2^H = 2.02$				

$A^- = \text{oxinate}, L = \text{vitamin U } \pm \text{ ion.}$

Conductivity water is used throughout the experimental work. Digital μ -361 pH-meter with readability ± 0.01 with combined glass calomel electrode has been used for potentiometry. Stoichiometrically 1 : 1 : 1 concentration of lanthanide(III), HA and HL is maintained in the solution. Five sets of the solutions were prepared containing (1) known amount of free $HClO_4$, (2) free $HClO_4$ + known amount of primary ligand, (3) free $HClO_4$ + known amount of secondary ligand, (4) free $HClO_4$ + known amount of primary ligand + known amount of metal perchlorate and (5) free $HClO_4$ + known amount of primary ligand + known amount of secondary ligand + known amount of metal perchlorate. Total volume of each mixture was raised to 50 ml using conductivity water. Some representative pH titration curves are presented in Fig. 1.

The values of proton ligand stability and metal ligand stability constants for lanthanide metal ion complexes with oxine and vitamin U at 25 °C and 35 °C are given in Table 1.

Conclusion :

The ternary complexes of La^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Sm^{3+} , and Gd^{3+} , with oxine and vitamin U ligand have been studied to determine their stability. It is interesting, because the order of the stability is governed by various factors

Fig. 1. Pr^{III} -oxine-vitamin U system temperature 25 ± 0.1 °C : (1) acid, (2) oxine, (3) vitamin U, (4) 1 : 1 molar ratio of Pr^{III} -oxine, (5) 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio of Pr^{III} -oxine-vitamin U

like stereochemistry, charge on metal ion, electronegativity, nature of metal ion and ligand. Hence, these data are very useful to study the various biochemical reactions.

References

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